

On the Thermoviscoelastic Characterization of Adhesives and Composites

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a method to characterize the time and temperature behavior of adhesives and polymeric resins within the linear range of stress-strain response.

The method involves an experimental scheme to determine in a non-ambiguous way if the time-dependent behavior is thermorheologically simple or complex and provides suitable analytical expressions to predict the behavior in either case. Some experimental results are discussed and the differences between the predictions of the thermorheologically simple and complex models are assessed for the particular data at hand.

The subject is related to the design of geometrically stable structures.

NOMENCLATURE

$a = a(T)$	Shift factor function
$D = D(t)$	Creep compliance
$D_0 = D_0(T)$	Terms in power-law creep
D_1	
$H^I = H(\cdot)$	Heaviside step function
$h = h(T)$	Horizontal shift function
n	Power term in power-law creep
r	Rate of temperature-rise
S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3	Empirical numerical factors
t	Time
T	Temperature
T^g	Glass transition temperature
T^g_R	Reference temperature (where $a=h=v_1=v_2=v=1$)
$v(T)$	Vertical shift function
$v_1(T), v_2(T)$	Vertical shift functions ($v_1, v_2 = v$)
α	Coefficient of thermal expansion
ϵ	Strain
ϵ_c	Creep strain
ϵ_r	Recovery strain (after unloading)
$\Delta\epsilon(t)$	Time-dependent portion of ϵ
σ	Stress
ξ, ζ	Reduced times

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that polymeric materials creep under steady loads (1). More recently such behavior was observed for fibrous composites loaded in shear and transversely to the fiber directions (2), (3), (4).

It is commonly recognized that at elevated temperatures the creep is enhanced and accelerated, it being generally assumed that the enhancement is due to modulus softening while the acceleration is caused by a reduction in viscosity. At temperatures above the glass-transition temperature, T_g , the thermal effects on deformation are almost exclusively related to reduction in viscosity and can thereby be represented strictly by "telescoping" the time-scale for creep. Mathematically, this means that if at some temperature, $T = T_R > T_g$, the creep strain under stress, σ_0 , is given by $\epsilon = \sigma_0 F(t)$ then at $T = T_E > T_R$, $\epsilon = \sigma_0 F(a(T)t)$. The empirically determined function $a(T)$ is called the "shift-factor" function because when isothermal creep data are plotted against $\log t$, one obtains $\epsilon(T, \log t) = \epsilon(T_R, \log t + \log a(T))$. Namely, $a(T)$ determines a shifted value along the abscissa and thus a horizontal distance between $\epsilon(T, \log t)$ and $\epsilon(T_R, \log t)$. Usually, for $T > T_R$, $\epsilon(T, t)$ is positioned to the left of $\epsilon(T_R, t)$. Similar conclusions apply to data plotted in the form of $\log \dot{\epsilon}$ vs. $\log t$.

The above mentioned type of response is denoted as "thermo-rheologically simple", or alternately referred to as the "time-temperature analogy". It has the appeal of simplicity and also the important advantage that it enables the solution of many boundary-value problems in linear viscoelasticity by direct reference to results from linear elasticity. For thermo-rheologically simple response, the so called "correspondence principle" applies to a wide class of problems.

A vast set of data were collected and reduced by means of the "time-temperature analogy", (1), (5) and employed in solving many boundary value problems (e.g. (6)). Schematically, such data appear in a form shown in Figure 1.

At temperatures below T_g , thermal effects on modulus softening cannot always be neglected. This phenomenon is revealed by the fact that isothermal creep data at various temperatures are plainly not relatable by a horizontal shift factor function $a(T)$ alone. In several cases, it was noted that a relationship could be established through empirically measured horizontal as well as vertical shifts (7)-(11). Schematically, such data appear in forms like shown in Figure 2.

Finally, the creep of many polymers can be represented by the so-called "power law" (12)-(15). It turns out that in this case, isothermal creep data collected at various temperatures can be correlated by either horizontal or vertical shifts, or a combination of both, and it is not a-priori clear which correlation is correct.

The question of the proper form of data representation is of great practical importance for two reasons: (1) the correct form of the vertical and horizontal shift functions is necessary to calculate response under transient stresses and temperatures, (2) the correct expression for the horizontal shift factor is essential for predicting long-time response from short time data taken at elevated temperatures. This is due to the fact that time and temperature may be interchangeable only through the amount of shift which occurs parallel to the $\log t$ axis. The effects of the vertical shift must, of course, be also considered because they scale the stress effects.

This paper outlines an analytical scheme and experimental procedure to sort out the vertical shift, quantify the temperature dependent horizontal and vertical shifts, and determine their appropriate incorporation in a superposition-integral for the case of transient stresses and temperatures.

ANALYSIS

(a) The General Case

Consider isothermal creep data as shown in Figure 2 and assume that these data were fitted to form a continuous "master curve" so that the creep at some reference temperature, T_R , can be extended and expressed by empirically determined functions $v(T)$ and $h(T)$ as follows:

Figure 1. Isothermal data suitable for horizontal shifting alone (schematic).

Figure 2. Isothermal data requiring both horizontal and vertical shifting (schematic).

$$\epsilon(t) = D(t, T)\sigma_0 = v(T)F(h(T)t)\sigma_0, \text{ where } D(t; T_R) = F(t). \quad (1)$$

In (1), $v(T)$ and $h(T)$ are the vertical and horizontal shift factors, respectively, T is temperature and t is time.

The empirically determined function $h(T)$ can be used to correlate long-time creep at low temperatures from short-time, elevated temperature, isothermal data. However, form (1) is too ambiguous to predict response under transient temperatures. This can be seen by noting that under fluctuating temperatures and stresses, the integral

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon(t) &= v_1(T(t)) \int_0^t F(\xi(t) - \xi(\tau)) \frac{d}{dt}(v_2(T(\tau))\sigma(\tau))d\tau \\ &+ \alpha[T(t) - T(0)] \\ \text{with } \xi(u) &= \int_0^u h(T(s))ds \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

will reduce to (1) in the isothermal case, with $\sigma(t) = \sigma_0 H(t)$, regardless of the functional forms of $v_1(T)$ and $v_2(T)$ as long as

$$v_1(T)v_2(T) = v(T) \quad (3)$$

It is seen that the function $v(T)$ alone does not suffice to characterize the viscoelastic behavior and additional experiments, beyond those of isothermal creep, are required to complete the task.

Consider, therefore, creep experiments under constant loads containing a sudden drop in temperature at time $t = t_1$, namely

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma(t) &= \sigma_0 H(t) \\ T(t) &= T_u - (T_u - T_d)H(t - t_1) \quad T_u > T_d \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Substituting (4) in (2) we get

$$\epsilon(t) = v_1(T_u)v_2(T_u)F(h(T_u)t)\sigma_0 \quad 0 < t < t_1 \quad (5)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon(t) = & v_1(T_d)[F(h(T_u)t_1 + h(T_d)(t - t_1))v_2(T_u) \\ & - F(h(T_d)(t - t_1))(v_2(T_u) - v_2(T_d))] \sigma_0 \\ & - \alpha(T_u - T_d) \quad t > t_1 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Let $T_d = T_R$ then, by hypothesis $v_1(T_R) = v_2(T_R) = h(T_R) = 1$. Also denote $T_u = T_0$ then (6) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon(t) = & \sigma_0 \left\{ [F(h(T_0)t_1 + t - t_1) - F(t - t_1)]v_2(T_0) + F(t - t_1) \right\} \\ & - \alpha(T_0 - T_R) \quad t > t_1 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

In (6) and (7), α designates the coefficient of thermal expansion.

With $\epsilon(t)$ in (7) measured experimentally, $v_2(T_0)$ can be determined, since all other quantities in (7) are assumed known from isothermal data. Obviously, we get $v_1(T_0) = v(T_0)/v_2(T_0)$.

The temperature level T_0 can now serve as T_d in eqn. (6) and thus obtain $v_2(T_u)$, whereby also $v_1(T_u)$, and so on. In such a manner, the forms of $v_1(T)$ and $v_2(T)$ can be established.

(b) Power-law Creep

Many polymeric resins and composites exhibit creep response that can be expressed as follows:

$$\epsilon(t) = [D_0(T) + D_1(a(T)t)^n] \sigma_0 \quad (8)$$

Denote the time-dependent portion of $\epsilon(t)$ by

$$\Delta\epsilon(t) = D_1(a(T)t)^n \sigma_0 \quad (9)$$

In view of (9), we get log-log plots as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The time-dependent portion $\Delta\epsilon(t)$ of the creep strain for a "power-law material", with power n , and the various possibilities of vertical and horizontal shifts.

It is thus noted that isothermal data reduces to straight, parallel lines, with slope n , separated by a horizontal distance $a(T)$. Elevated-temperature data can be related to reference-temperature creep through a horizontal shift $a(T)$, but a vertical shift $v(T) = na(T)$ is equally possible. Any combination of a horizontal shift $h(T) = [a(T)]^q$ and a vertical shift $v(T) = [a(T)]^{n(1-q)}$ is also acceptable (see Figure 3). We, therefore, note that for power-law creep, isothermal data alone does not determine the functions $v(T)$ and $h(T)$. Obviously, the "components" $v_1(T)$ and $v_2(T)$ must also be sorted out subject to the condition $v_1 v_2 = v$.

Let us consider the most general form which applied now

$$\Delta \epsilon(t) = D_1 v_1(T(t)) \int_0^t [\zeta(t) - \zeta(\tau)]^n \frac{d}{d\tau} [v_2(T(\tau)) \sigma(\tau)] d\tau \quad (10)$$

where

$$\zeta(u) = \int_0^u [h(T(s))] ds \quad (11)$$

with

$$h(T) = a(T)^q(T)$$

Also, $v(T) = v_1(T)v_2(T) = [a(T)]^{n(1-q)}$ and we assume that $0 \leq q(T) \leq 1$. It can be readily observed that for $\sigma = \sigma_0 H(t)$ and $T = \text{const.}$ (10) reduces to $\Delta \epsilon(t) = D_1 [a(T)t]^n \sigma_0$ for any v_1, v_2, h and q . Similarly, isothermal behavior under fluctuating stress is insensitive to v_1, v_2, h and q .

As an aside, let us consider the case $\sigma = \sigma_0 H(t)$, but $T = T(t)$. Employing (10) with $q = 1$, i.e. only a horizontal shift, we get

$$\Delta \tilde{\epsilon}(t) = D_1 \int_0^t a(T(s)) ds]^n \sigma_0 = D_1 [a(T(t))]^n \int_0^t \frac{a(T(s))}{a(T(t))} ds]^n \sigma_0 \quad (12)$$

On the other hand, if we set $q = 0$, i.e. only vertical shift, we get

$$\Delta \tilde{\epsilon}(t) = D_1 v(T(t)) [\zeta(t)]^n = D_1 [a(T(t))]^n t^n \sigma_0 \quad (13)$$

All presently available data indicate that $a(T)$ increases monotonically with T . Therefore, comparing (12) and (13) we note that $\Delta \tilde{\epsilon}(t) < \Delta \tilde{\epsilon}(t)$ for all monotonically increasing temperature histories and $\Delta \tilde{\epsilon}(t) < \Delta \tilde{\epsilon}(t)$ for all decreasing temperatures.

Returning to our main theme, consider isothermal creep and recovery behavior. Namely, let $T = T_0 = \text{const.}$

$$\sigma(t) = \sigma_0 [H(t) - H(t - t_1)] \quad (14)$$

In view of (8) and (10) we obtain

$$\epsilon_c = \{D_0(T_0) + D_1 [a(T_0)t]^n\} \sigma_0 \quad 0 < t < t_1 \quad (15)$$

$$\epsilon_r = [a(T_0)]^n [t^n - (t - t_1)^n] \sigma_0 \quad t > t_1 \quad (16)$$

From (15) and (16) it is possible to determine $D_0(T_0)$, D_1 , $a(T_0)$ and n according to well established procedures (11), (14), (15), (16).

Consider next creep under constant stress and temperature, followed by recovery after a simultaneous removal of the load and abrupt cool-down. Namely,

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 [H(t) - H(t - t_1)] \quad (17)$$

$$T = T_0 - (T_0 - T_R) H(t - t_1)$$

By hypothesis, $v_1 = v_2 = h = 1$ at $T = T_R$, whereby we obtain

$$\epsilon_r = D_1 v_2(T_0) \left\{ [h(T_0)t_1 + t - t_1]^n - (t - t_1)^n \right\} \sigma_0 - \alpha(T_0 - T_R) \quad (18)$$

Employing curve fitting routines, it is possible to determine $v_2(T_0)$ and $h(T_0)$ by matching (18) against recovery data. It is, of course, advisable to conduct tests with several time-intervals t_1 . With $a(T_0)$, $h(T_0)$, $v_2(T_0)$ known, it is possible to evaluate $v_1(T_0)$.

Abrupt variations in load and temperature obviously introduce transient effects. However, it appears possible to limit the duration of transients to

about 10-15 sec. by selecting sufficiently thin tests coupons.

With v_1 , v_2 , and h known at T_0 we can replace T_R in (17) with $T_d = T_0$ and T_0 in (17) with T_u , and so on, to cover the range of temperatures of interest, in just the same manner as for the "general case".

EXPERIMENTAL DATA AND COMPUTATIONAL COMPARISONS

Creep and recovery data were collected for FM-73 adhesive. This is a rubber-particle reinforced epoxy cured at about 120°C, with $T_g \sim 80^\circ\text{C}$ and with ultimate tensile stress $\sigma_u \sim 50$ MPa. The coefficient of thermal expansion was found to be constant, with $\alpha = 6.6 \times 10^{-5}$ m/m/1°C. For stresses up to 10 MPa, the response is linear.

The experiments, which are described in full detail elsewhere, (11), (16) covered temperatures in the range 30°C-60°C.

Measurements were recorded for 7" x 0.45" x 0.07" coupons with the aid of "EP Series" strain gages. Isothermal creep and recovery data were collected by means of creep frames at $T = 30^\circ\text{C}$, 40°C , 50°C , and 60°C . Abrupt cool-down tests were performed within an Instron environmental chamber attached to an MTS machine. Creep was recorded, typically, for 15 minutes and recovery during 10 additional minutes. The cool-down tests involved temperature drops between various combinations of the above-mentioned temperature levels. Cooling was accomplished by pumping pressurized CO_2 gas into the environmental chamber with concurrent heating of the chamber to counterbalance any over-cooling. The entire process was controlled manually, maintaining good control to within $\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and limiting the transient state of strains to within ten seconds. The confinement of transients to such a short time span was accomplished by the judicious selection of 0.07" thickness for the coupons.

Each and every test was repeated five times to ascertain the reliability of the data. Scatter was limited to about $\pm 4\%$.

The data were reduced by means of a power-law expression and analyzed according to the method described above. We obtained:

$$D_1 = 29 \times 10^{-6} \text{ (with time measured in seconds), } n = 0.12$$

$$D_0(T) = 360 \times 10^{-6} [1 + 0.91(T - T_R)/T_R] (\text{MPa})^{-1} \text{ with } T \text{ in degrees}$$

$$\text{Kelvin and } T_R = 303^\circ\text{K}.$$

Also, $h = \exp [S_0(T - T_R)/T_R]$, $v_1 = \exp [-S_1(T - T_R)/T_R]$, $v_2 = \exp [S_2(T - T_R)/T_R]$ with $S_0 = 40$, $S_1 = 8.5$, $S_2 = 12.12$.

Upon completion of the characterization tests, we measured creep at $\sigma = 10$ MPa with linearly varying temperature $T = T_R + 0.0083t$.

The results are shown by the heavy, solid line in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Creep at $\sigma = 10H(t)$ (MPa) under linearly varying temperature $T = T_R + rt$. Experimental results and theoretical predictions (thick and thin lines).

It is interesting to note that if the vertical shifts were erroneously discarded and replaced by an equivalent horizontal shift, namely if one takes

$$a(T) = \exp[S_3(T - T_R)/T_R] \quad , \quad S_3 = S_0 + (S_1 - S_2)/n \quad (20)$$

and

$$v_1(T) = v_2(T) = 1$$

then the resulting expression for strain is

$$\epsilon(t) = \{D_0(T(t)) + D_1(\xi(t))^n\} \sigma_0 + \alpha(T(t) - T_R) \quad (21)$$

yielding values of $\epsilon(t)$ almost indistinguishable from (19).

Similar circumstances occur whenever the temperature fluctuations are relatively slow, up to about 1-2°C/min. In all such cases, the errors involved by employment of eqns. (20) instead of (10) are equivalent in magnitude to the data scatter.

On the other hand, under sharp temperature fluctuations, a deletion of the vertical shifts can lead to discrepancies of 25% - 30% in the predictions of creep strain. Such cases are shown in Figures 5, 7, and 8. In Figure 5, the strain due to $\sigma = \sigma_0 H(t)$ and $T = T_0 H(t) - (T_0 - T_R) H(t - t_0)$ is shown vs. time t . $\sigma_0 = 10$ MPa, $T_0 = 60^\circ\text{C}$, $T_R = 30^\circ\text{C}$ and $t_0 = 1500$ sec. The results shown by solid lines incorporate both vertical and horizontal shifts, while the dotted lines are based on the horizontal shift only as given in (20).

Figure 6 shows a temperature profile T vs. time t used in evaluating the strain in Figure 7 and 8. The strain in Figure 7 is evaluated for one cycle $T(t)$ shown in Figure 6 followed by $T = T_R = 30^\circ\text{C}$ for $t \geq 4000$ sec. The strain in Figure 8 corresponds to four cycles of the temperature profile $T(t)$ in Figure 6.

In both Figures 7 and 8, $\sigma = \sigma_0 H(t)$, $\sigma_0 = 10$ MPa. The solid lines in Figures 7 and 8 correspond to both vertical and horizontal shifts while the dashed lines are computed on the basis of horizontal shifts only.

Figure 5. Creep at $\sigma = 10H(t)$ (MPa) with temperature $T = T_0 H(t) - (T_0 - T_R) H(t - t_0)$. Predictions based on horizontal and vertical shifts (solid line) and on horizontal shift alone (dashed line).

Figure 6. Temperature history segment employed in Figures 7 and 8.

Figure 7. Creep at $\sigma = 10H(t)$ (MPa) under temperature T as in Figure 6, followed by $T = T_R$ for $t > 4000$ sec solid and dashed lines as in Figure 5.

Figure 8. Creep at $\sigma = 10H(t)$ (MPa) under four sequential cycles of the temperature shown in Figure 6, solid and dashed lines as in Figure 5.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

This work demonstrated that isothermal creep data may be insufficient to characterize the thermoviscoelastic response of polymers below T_g (unless it is possible to form master curves by horizontal shifts alone). In many cases, additional transient-temperature data are required for the proper formulation of the time-temperature behavior. Illustrations were provided to demonstrate the importance of a complete thermo-viscoelastic characterization, showing that discrepancies of up to 30% may arise by using an incomplete characterization. Similar circumstances may occur in polymeric composites.

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